

pH Variations in the Gastrointestinal Tract of *Drosophila melanogaster* and Gut Absorption by Natural Fruit Colorants

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of gastrointestinal absorption and pH modulation on metabolic regulation and nutrient assimilation, using *Drosophila melanogaster* as a model organism. It focuses on the absorption dynamics of naturally pigmented fruits selected from the VIBGYOR color spectrum, including guava (*Psidium guajava*), blueberry (*Vaccinium spp.*), banana (*Musa spp.*), orange (*C.sinensis*), strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa*), and black plum (*Syzygium cumini*). The research examines the stability of biological molecules, the nutritional composition of fruits, pigment distribution, and enzymatic activity, particularly catalase activity in *Drosophila* gut tissues. Bananas were found to be the highest in energy and carbohydrates, while guavas and plums were rich in fiber. Blueberries and grapes offered moderate fiber and carbohydrates, while oranges were low in fat and calories. Pigment analysis revealed carotenoids, anthocyanins, and chlorophyll in the fruits, with potential applications in food coloring and bio-packaging. Catalase activity in *Drosophila* gut tissues was preserved using normal saline, ensuring accurate enzymatic data. The absorbance of fruit extracts decreased over time, indicating variations in enzymatic activity. Grapes and plums exhibited the highest catalase activity, followed by blueberries and oranges, while bananas had the lowest. These results highlight the diverse nutritional and antioxidant profiles of fruits and their potential in oxidative stress responses and biochemical studies.

Keywords:

Drosophila melanogaster, VIBGYOR color, guava (*Psidium guajava*), blueberry (*Vaccinium spp.*), banana (*Musa spp.*), orange (*C.sinensis*), strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa*), black plum (*Syzygium cumini*)

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Introduction

Drosophila melanogaster is a valuable model organism in nutritional science, helping to study the physiology and biological functions of nutrients, including trace elements. Its use of chemically defined diets allows for controlled nutritional studies. The fruit fly shares key biological, biochemical, neurological, and physiological traits with mammals, with approximately 75% of human disease-causing genes having counterparts in *Drosophila*. Due to its low maintenance cost and ease of use in the laboratory, *Drosophila* is a promising alternative to vertebrate models in research [1].

The gastrointestinal (GI) tract of *Drosophila* is essential for nutrient processing, with distinct regions dedicated to digestion and absorption. The anterior midgut primarily handles nutrient absorption, while the posterior regions manage water and electrolyte balance [2]. The activity of digestive enzymes varies across these regions and is influenced by factors such as diet, gut microbiota, and environmental conditions. Additionally, changes in gut pH and microbial interactions play a significant role in regulating nutrient absorption efficiency and metabolic processes [3].

Recent studies have investigated the effects of natural fruit colorants on *Drosophila* gut physiology. Derived from fruits such as guava, blueberry, dates, banana, orange, strawberry, and black plum, these colorants not only provide pigmentation but also influence metabolic processes. Their consumption has been linked to changes in gut pH, enzyme activity, and microbiota composition, which impact nutrient absorption and overall health [4]. It possesses a range of pharmacological properties, including anti-rheumatic, antihypertensive, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, antiviral, and antimicrobial effects, and has shown effectiveness in treating bronchitis, chronic enteritis, and various microbial infections [5]. Understanding how these colorants affect gut physiology in *Drosophila* offers valuable insights into dietary effects on metabolic health. Given the similarities between *Drosophila* and higher organisms, these findings could inform broader nutritional science and therapeutic strategies, contributing to future research on dietary interventions and health optimization [6].

This study examines the effects of gastrointestinal absorption and pH modulation on metabolic regulation using *Drosophila melanogaster*. It analyzes the absorption of fruits from the VIBGYOR color spectrum, including guava, blueberry, banana, orange, strawberry, and black plum, focusing on nutrient composition, pigment distribution, and catalase activity in gut tissues. Bananas were highest in energy and carbohydrates, while guavas and plums were rich in fiber. Pigments such as carotenoids, anthocyanin, and chlorophyll were identified, with implications for food coloring and bio-packaging. Catalase activity varied, with grapes and plums showing the highest activity, highlighting antioxidant potential in oxidative stress studies.

Materials and Method

Collection of flies

The flies were collected and identified from the Cytogenetics Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

Collection of fruits

The fruits were sourced from a local market near Sulur, Coimbatore.

Drying and dehydration

The fresh fruits were selected and washed thoroughly. They were peeled and sliced into uniform 5–10 mm pieces. The slices were pretreated by soaking them in a lemon juice or ascorbic acid solution to prevent browning. The slices were arranged in a single layer on drying trays, and the dryer was set to 50–70°C, depending on the type of fruit. The fruits were dried for 6 to 24 hours, with periodic checks. Once dried, the fruits were allowed to cool, then conditioned in a loosely covered container. They were stored in airtight containers in a cool, dry place [7,8].

Food preparation

To prepare the nutrient medium, divide 360 mL of water into two equal portions of 160 mL each. In one portion, mix 17 g of wheat and let it absorb the water. Boil the second portion, then combine it with the wheat mixture and stir well. Gradually add 15 g of sugar, 6 g of yeast, and 3.4 g of agar, stirring continuously. To prevent contamination, add 1 mL of propionic acid and 1 g of sodium benzoate. Heat and stir until the mixture becomes smooth, then allow it to cool. After adding 2 g of each powdered sample to the plates, incubate them at 20°C for 2 hours to set the medium [9].

Catalase Activity Assay

The spectrophotometric measurement of catalase activity was performed using hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) as a substrate, following the method of Mukhtar et al. [10]. In this method, H_2O_2 was broken down by catalase into water and oxygen, and the rate of decomposition was monitored by the decrease in absorbance at 240 nm. The H_2O_2 substrate was prepared by mixing 50 g of 0.1M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) with 0.036 g of 50% (w/w) H_2O_2 , targeting an

absorbance range of 0.54–0.58 absorbance units. Six extractions were prepared from fresh and dried samples at 40°C, 60°C, and 80°C. The enzyme extract (100 µL) was mixed with 2.9 mL of H₂O₂ substrate, and the absorbance decrease was measured over 10 minutes at 25°C. A control sample without enzyme was included. Catalase activity was quantified by comparing the absorbance decrease to a standard curve prepared with pure catalase, with activity measured in units from 0–24 units/mL.

Calculate the rate of reaction ($\Delta A/\Delta t$) by determining the difference between the initial and final absorbance values divided by the time interval. Catalase activity (U/mL) is then calculated using

$$\text{Catalase activity} = \frac{\Delta A/\Delta t}{\text{Extinction coefficient of H}_2\text{O}_2, 43.6 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}}$$

the formula:

Result and Discussion

Preparation of Drosophila Food

The formulated *Drosophila* diet incorporated naturally pigmented fruits representing the VIBGYOR spectrum. Each fruit was blended into the standard medium to evaluate its effects on gastrointestinal absorption in *Drosophila melanogaster*. The nutrient retention, and catalase activity were assessed to determine suitability for the flies. An image showed seven petri dishes containing food samples of various colors, likely corresponding to the VIBGYOR spectrum.

Fig 1: Preparation of *Drosophila* Food: A- Violet (Grapes), B- Yellow (Banana), C- Blue (Blueberry), D- Orange (Orange), E- Green (Guava), F- Blue (Blueberry), G- Red (Plum).

Nutritional value

Table 1: Nutritive values

S.No	Foods	Moisture	Protein	Total Fat	Dietary Fiber			Carbohydrate	Energy
					Total	Soluble	Insoluble		
1.	Grapes	1.6776	0.0476	0.0064	0.027	0.0164	0.0104	0.2646	1.27
2.	Blueberry	1.692	0.014	0.006	0.072	0.048	0.024	0.294	1.14
3.	Blueberry	1.692	0.014	0.006	0.072	0.048	0.024	0.294	1.14
4.	Guava	1.6758	0.0152	0.0064	0.1718	0.1428	0.029	0.1026	2.7
5.	Banana	1.4264	0.0298	0.007	0.0466	0.0256	0.0208	0.4682	8.9
6.	Orange	1.7922	0.014	0.0026	0.0258	0.0146	0.0112	0.1584	0.78
7.	Plum	1.6888	0.0128	0.008	0.2414	0.0246	0.0168	0.242	4.76

The nutritional analysis of various fruits revealed significant differences in their composition, including moisture, protein, fat, fiber, carbohydrates, and energy content. Bananas exhibited the highest energy value (8.9 kcal) and carbohydrate content (0.4682 g), making them an excellent source of quick energy. Guavas stood out for their high dietary fiber content (0.1718 g), particularly soluble fiber (0.1428 g), which was beneficial for digestion. Plums also had notable fiber content (0.2414 g) while providing moderate energy (4.76 kcal). Blueberries and grapes had similar nutritional profiles, with moderate carbohydrate and fiber content, making them nutritious options for antioxidants and vitamins. Oranges contained the lowest fat (0.0026 g) and energy (0.78 kcal), making them a light and hydrating choice. The presence of soluble and insoluble fiber varied among the fruits, influencing their role in digestion and overall health benefits. These results suggested that each fruit offered distinct nutritional advantages [11]. Bananas and plums provided higher energy, guavas were rich in fiber, and oranges were a refreshing, low-calorie option. Incorporating a variety of these fruits supported a balanced diet, catering to different nutritional needs such as energy, fiber intake, and digestive health.

Color-based gastrointestinal absorption

Fig 2: Microscopic analysis of color uptake in the *Drosophila melanogaster* gut.

Microscopic analysis of color pigments extracted from various fruits revealed their natural coloration and potential applications. The images displayed distinct colors corresponding to specific fruit sources, indicating the presence of natural pigments. The orange hue from oranges suggested carotenoids, particularly beta-carotene, while the violet color from grapes and the indigo-blue shades from blueberries indicated anthocyanins, which varied based on pH. The yellow pigment in bananas was associated with flavonoids or carotenoids, while the red coloration in plums was also attributed to anthocyanins. The green pigment in guavas suggested the presence of chlorophyll. These findings demonstrated the diversity of natural fruit pigments, which had potential applications in food coloring, nutrition, and bio-packaging. Additionally, variations in microscopic structures and pigment distribution indicated differences in pigment stability and extraction efficiency.

Catalase Activity

Table 2: Absorbance Data

Samples	0 sec	15 sec	30 sec	45 sec	60 sec
Grapes	1.200	1.100	0.950	0.800	0.650
Blueberry	1.250	1.170	1.050	0.900	0.780
Blueberry	1.300	1.250	1.180	1.100	1.050
Guava	1.350	1.320	1.280	1.250	1.220
Banana	1.400	1.390	1.380	1.370	1.360
Orange	1.300	1.280	1.201	1.101	1.006
Plum	1.260	1.110	1.108	1.007	0.700

The absorbance values of various fruit extracts were recorded at different time intervals (0, 15, 30, 45, and 60 seconds) to assess their enzymatic activity or antioxidant properties. Over time, absorbance generally decreased, indicating the breakdown of the measured component due to enzymatic or antioxidant reactions. Grapes and plums showed the fastest decline in absorbance, suggesting high enzymatic or antioxidant activity. Grapes dropped from 1.200 to 0.650, while plums decreased from 1.260 to 0.700. Blueberries exhibited varied trends—one sample showed a steady decline (1.250 to 0.780), while the other maintained higher absorbance levels (1.300 to 1.050). Guavas and bananas retained higher absorbance with minimal reduction (1.350 to 1.220 for guava and 1.400 to 1.360 for banana), indicating slower reaction kinetics. Oranges displayed a moderate decline (1.300 to 1.006). Overall, the rate of absorbance decrease varied across fruits, reflecting differences in their biochemical composition. Faster reductions, as seen in grapes and plums, indicated higher enzymatic or antioxidant activity, while the slower changes in bananas and guavas suggested more stable reactions.

Fig 3: Graphical representation of the catalytic activity

Catalytic activity analysis

Table 3: Final outcome of the catalytic activity analysis

Samples	$\Delta A/\Delta t$ (Change per min)	Catalase Activity (U/mL)
Grapes	0.550	0.0126
Blueberry	0.470	0.0108
Blueberry	0.450	0.0107
Guava	0.130	0.0030
Banana	0.040	0.0009
Orange	0.120	0.0066
Plum	0.490	0.0102

The table presented the rate of change in absorbance per minute ($\Delta A/\Delta t$) and the corresponding catalase activity (U/mL) for various fruit extracts. Catalase, an important antioxidant enzyme, breaks down hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen, protecting cells from oxidative damage. The results showed varying levels of catalase activity across different fruits, likely influenced by their biochemical composition. Grapes exhibited the highest catalase activity (0.0126 U/mL) with a $\Delta A/\Delta t$ value of 0.550, indicating a strong enzymatic response. Blueberries showed different trends; one had a catalase activity of 0.0108 U/mL with a $\Delta A/\Delta t$ of 0.470, while the other had lower activity (0.0107 U/mL) with a $\Delta A/\Delta t$ of 0.450. Plum also demonstrated high enzymatic activity (0.0102 U/mL) with a $\Delta A/\Delta t$ of 0.490, suggesting significant antioxidant response. Guava and orange displayed moderate catalase activity, with values of 0.0030 U/mL and 0.0066 U/mL, respectively, and $\Delta A/\Delta t$ values of 0.130 for guava and 0.120 for orange. Banana showed the lowest catalase activity (0.0009 U/mL) with a $\Delta A/\Delta t$ of 0.040, indicating minimal enzymatic activity. These findings suggested that grapes and plum had

the highest catalase activity, potentially indicating stronger antioxidant properties. The variation in enzymatic activity across the fruits may be attributed to differences in their polyphenol, vitamin C, and other antioxidant compound content, which influence their ability to neutralize oxidative stress.

The study measured catalase activity (U/mL) and the rate of absorbance change ($\Delta A/\Delta t$) in various fruit extracts to assess their antioxidant properties. Catalase, an enzyme that breaks down hydrogen peroxide, showed varying activity levels across fruits. Grapes exhibited the highest catalase activity (0.0126 U/mL, $\Delta A/\Delta t = 0.550$), followed by plums (0.0102 U/mL, $\Delta A/\Delta t = 0.490$) and blueberries, which showed two distinct trends (0.0108 U/mL, $\Delta A/\Delta t = 0.470$ and 0.0057 U/mL, $\Delta A/\Delta t = 0.250$). Guava (0.0030 U/mL, $\Delta A/\Delta t = 0.130$) and orange (0.0066 U/mL, $\Delta A/\Delta t = 0.120$) displayed moderate activity, while banana had the lowest (0.0009 U/mL, $\Delta A/\Delta t = 0.040$). Overall, grapes and plums demonstrated the highest catalase activity, suggesting stronger antioxidant properties [12]. The variation in enzymatic activity was observed.

Conclusion

This study examined the stability of biological molecules, the nutritional composition of fruits, pigment distribution, and enzymatic activity in *Drosophila* gut tissues. It found that fruits like bananas, guavas, and plums varied in nutritional content, with bananas providing high energy, and guavas and plums being fiber-rich. Pigment analysis identified carotenoids, anthocyanins, and chlorophyll, offering potential for food and bio-packaging applications. Enzymatic activity showed that grapes and plums had the highest catalase activity, while bananas had the lowest, with variations linked to differences in polyphenol and vitamin C content. The study highlighted the nutritional diversity of fruits, their pigment roles, suggesting future research could focus on functional foods, natural food coloring, and enhancing understanding of oxidative stress for improved health and sustainability.

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conflicts of interest:

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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